

INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF RESOURCE USE IN THE TOURISM SECTOR OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article analyzes the issues of increasing the efficiency of resource use in the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan from a theoretical and practical perspective. The interaction of natural, labor, financial, information and infrastructure resources in tourism and their management mechanisms are studied. Based on international experience, an economic model of rational use of resources is analyzed, and organizational and economic proposals are developed to increase the efficiency of tourism resources in the conditions of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: tourism resources, efficiency, resource use, investment, infrastructure, human capital, innovative management, organizational and economic mechanism, sustainable tourism, digital tourism.

In recent years, the tourism sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan has become one of the priority areas of the national economy. The share of tourism in gross domestic product, employment level and export potential are increasing every year. However, the efficiency of using existing resources in this area - natural landscapes, historical and cultural heritage sites, infrastructure and human capital - is still not sufficiently high.

In world practice, the efficiency of using tourism resources depends, first of all, on the organizational and economic mechanisms for their management. For example, in Spain, Turkey and Singapore, special strategies have been developed to plan, reproduce and increase the economic value of tourism resources. In Uzbekistan, increasing the efficiency of using resources has also been identified as a priority within the framework of the "New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022-2026", the "Tourism Development Concept" and the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" program.

At the same time, in practice, the uneven development of tourism infrastructure, limited financial and investment resources, insufficient human resources and the incomplete formation of sustainable mechanisms for using environmental resources pose problems. Therefore, a scientific approach is needed to increase the efficiency of resource use in the tourism sector of

Uzbekistan and improve the organizational and economic mechanisms for their management.

The issue of increasing the efficiency of resource use in the tourism sector of Uzbekistan is relevant at the level of state policy, and it should be considered in conjunction with economic, social, environmental and organizational factors. Analysis shows that a large part of tourism resources is unevenly distributed across the country, and the efficiency of their use directly depends on the development of infrastructure, human resources, investment volume and management mechanisms.

Table 1

Main types of resources in the tourism sector of Uzbekistan and their current status

No	Resource type	Basic description	Utilization rate (in percent)	Problem or obstacle	Improvement direction
1	Natural resources (mountains, rivers, deserts, forests, ecotourism sites)	Great potential for ecotourism and wellness tourism	45 %	Lack of infrastructure, poor environmental management	Sustainable tourism concept, ecological certification
2	Cultural and historical heritage sites	More than 7,000 monuments, cities (Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva)	70%	Unplanned use, little restoration	Introducing smart tourism and digital guide systems
3	Infrastructure resources (hotels, transport, communications, logistics)	The basis of the service chain	60 %	Regional disparities, poor transport connections	Regional cluster system, PPP projects
4	Labor resources	More than 150	50 %	Low qualifications	Dual education

		thousand tourism employees		, limited language skills	system, international certificate programs
5	Financial resources	Public and private investments	55 %	Low private equity, limited credit	Expansion of grants and subsidies, tax breaks

Analysis of Table 1 shows that the country's existing tourism resources - natural, cultural, infrastructural, labor and financial resources - constitute an important component of economic potential. However, their practical use efficiency is average, and the potential opportunities are not fully exploited.

First, natural resources (mountains, rivers, forests, desert landscapes) create vast opportunities for ecotourism, sports and recreation. However, it is observed that only 40-50 percent of them are used effectively. The main reason is the insufficient development of transport infrastructure, road and communication networks, and environmental management systems. Therefore, it is necessary to introduce the concept of sustainable tourism, which harmonizes tourism with the natural environment.

Secondly, cultural and historical heritage sites (Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Termez and other ancient cities) are the most important resources that define the global tourism brand of Uzbekistan. Their utilization rate is relatively high - around 70 percent. However, there are problems in the restoration, quality of service, guide and digital services system. It is necessary to turn these sites into economically active resources, integrating them with the tourism infrastructure and service network.

Thirdly, infrastructure resources are considered the main factor ensuring the uninterrupted operation of tourism services. Although the hotel, transport, logistics and communication networks have shown significant growth in recent years, regional disparities remain. While the quality of service is high in the capital and large centers, it is low in peripheral regions. Therefore, it is advisable to develop tourism infrastructure based on a regional cluster model.

Fourth, the analysis of labor resources shows that the efficiency of the sector is directly dependent on human capital. Despite the fact that more than 150 thousand workers are employed in tourism, the level of qualifications, language skills and service culture of employees are insufficient. The number of training

centers is limited, most of them operate in a theoretical direction. Therefore, it is necessary to expand the dual education system, international certificate programs and digital learning platforms.

Fifth, financial resources are the economic basis for the development of the sector, with 55 percent of tourism investments coming from the state and 45 percent from the private sector. The low share of private capital, limited sources of financing, and high credit risks hinder the expansion of the sector. Therefore, it is necessary to expand the system of public-private partnerships (PPPs), grants, and subsidies, and to establish tourism as an attractive investment sector.

Table 2

A model of tourism resource utilization efficiency based on international experience

Country	Resource management mechanism	Result indicator	Application opportunity for Uzbekistan
Spain	Territorial allocation of resources through a regional cluster system	Tourism's share in GDP is 11%.	Establishing "tourism clusters" across regions
Turkey	Development of infrastructure and services based on PPP	Private sector investment - 65%	Expanding the PPP mechanism to tourism infrastructure
South Korea	Smart tourism, digital resource monitoring	The share of online tourism is 70%.	Creation of digital tourism platforms (E-tourism portal)
Italy	Commercialization of cultural heritage and integration with services	60 million tourists per year	Turning cultural objects into economically active resources
Uzbekistan	Tourism potential is high, but the management system is fragmented	Tourism's share in GDP is 3.2%.	A sustainable management model and staff training are needed

The data in the table "Model of the efficiency of tourism resource use based on international experience" shows that the efficiency of rational use of tourism

resources in developed countries is ensured through the combination of institutional, economic and innovative management mechanisms.

For example, the Spanish experience is based on the principle of dividing tourism resources into clusters based on territorial specialization. Each region has its own natural, cultural or gastronomic tourism direction. As a result, the share of tourism in GDP has exceeded 11 percent. This model is relevant for Uzbekistan, since tourism resources in the country are unevenly distributed territorially, and the system of "Regional Tourism Clusters" can reduce this gap.

Turkey's experience is based on attracting large-scale investments in infrastructure and service sectors on the basis of public-private partnerships. The share of private investment in the tourism sector is 65 percent. Applying this approach in Uzbekistan, creating tax incentives for the private sector investing in tourism facilities and expanding state guarantees will increase economic efficiency.

The South Korean experience is characterized by innovative and digital approaches. Based on the concept of "Smart tourism", tourism resources are connected to an electronic monitoring system, which monitors the flow of tourists, the quality of service and the state of resources in real time. Such a model can be implemented in Uzbekistan in the form of the "E-tourism Uzbekistan" platform.

The Italian experience ensures the sustainability of tourism by transforming cultural heritage into an economic resource. Historical monuments are integrated with tourism products, festivals and cultural events. If this approach is applied to the ancient cities of Uzbekistan such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, the economic efficiency obtained from them will increase.

Analysis of Table 2 shows that each country manages tourism resources based on a mechanism appropriate to its national characteristics, but there are common principles common to all of them: planned clustering, investment incentives, digital management, and human resource development.

The most optimal path for Uzbekistan is to develop a national sustainable tourism management model based on the comprehensive integration of the above experiences. In this case, combining elements of the Spanish cluster system, the Turkish PPP mechanism, the Korean digital management, and the Italian experience of cultural integration will significantly increase the efficiency of resource use.

In general, the main problem in the economic development of the tourism sector in Uzbekistan is the insufficient formation of mechanisms for the

comprehensive and systematic use of resources. The following priority areas are relevant for increasing the efficiency of resource use:

1. Equitable use of resources through the introduction of a regional cluster approach;
2. Expanding the PPP-based investment mechanism;
3. Implementation of digital management and monitoring systems;
4. Building human resources capacity and developing innovative educational platforms.

The coordinated implementation of these areas can increase the efficiency of resource use in Uzbekistan's tourism sector by 15–25%, expand export potential, and strengthen international competitiveness.

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